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ANALYSIS AND CLINICAL STUDY OF SURGICAL MANAGEMENT AND OUTCOME OF BLUNT ABDOMINAL TRAUMA

Dr. RAVI V. SATASIA (MS)*, Dr. SANJAY R. CHAUHAN (MS), Dr. AIMANHUSEN M. PAYALA (MBBS)***, Dr. AARSH PANCHAL (MBBS)***, Dr. JAYKUMAR PATEL (MBBS)***, Dr. KULDEEP VANVI (MBBS)*****

*PROFESSOR & HEAD OF UNIT, **ASSISTANT PROFESSOR, ***RESIDENT DOCTOR MS, DEPARTMENT OF GENERAL SURGERY, SHETH LALLUBHAI GORDHANDAS MUNICIPAL GENERAL HOSPITAL, affiliated to AMC MET MEDICAL COLLEGE, MANINAGAR, AHMEDABAD, INDIA.

*Dr. Ravi Satasia: rsatasia@yahoo.com

**Dr. Sanjay Chauhan: drsanjaychauhan209@gmail.com

***Dr. Aimanhusen Payala: aimanpayla@gmail.com

***Dr. Aarsh Panchal: ampanchal96@gmail.com

***Dr. Kuldeep Vanvi: kuldeepvanvi@gmail.com

***Dr. Jaykumar Patel: jay.vil5830@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

INTRODUCTION:

Trauma during Road Traffic Accident is a major public health problem in all countries. It causes death, disability or both. 50% die immediately at the time of accident. 25% die in golden hour (4–6 hours) of trauma. 25% may die late during treatment period due to sepsis and complications.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

1)To study the impact of blunt abdominal trauma on abdominal solid organs like spleen, liver and hollow viscera like stomach and intestine along with various mode of injuries and their different type of management and their outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This is a prospective study of blunt abdominal injuries during the period from June 2019 to January 2021 in Sheth Lallubhai Gordhandas Municipal General Hospital, Ahmedabad. Number of cases studied is 60. Clinical Data of admitted patient were collected by their detail history after stabilizing the patient, clinical examination with appropriate investigations.

RESULTS AND DISSCUSION:

In our Study majority of the patients belonged to 21-30 years' age group, followed by 31-40 years' age group. 46 cases were males, with females accounting for only about 14 cases. 35 patients were operated and 25 patients were selected for non-operative management. Road traffic accident was responsible for 48% of blunt abdominal trauma cases, while fall from heights accounted for 18% of cases and blow with blunt object was responsible for 34% of injuries. Majority of the patients presented with abdominal pain (100%) and abdominal tenderness (76%). Average latent period was between 12-18 hours. Majority of patients (50%) were taken for surgery between 6-10 hours of latent period. Associated extra abdominal injuries were found in 27 cases. Apart from routine investigations, abdomen x ray was done in all patients. Ultrasound of abdomen was done in 53 cases. CT scan was done in 21 cases.

CONCLUSION:

Propper clinical examination and appropriate investigations helps in management of patient either operative or non-operative which leads successful treatment in these patients. Other associated injuries greatly influence the outcome in morbidity and mortality.

KEY WORDS: Blunt abdominal trauma; Road Traffic Accident; Spleen; Ultrasonography; CECT scan; Conservative Management; Post-operative complications; Mortality.

INTRODUCTION

In younger populations trauma is major leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. It is calculated that by the year 2020, 8.1 million people will lose their life as a result of severe injuries, and road traffic accidents (RTA) So RTA will be the third-most common cause of disabilities globally and the second-most common cause in developing countries. [1][2][3] Injuries may be penetrating, blunt, blast, chemical, electrical and other injuries. In road traffic accidents Motor vehicle accidents are mainstay of blunt abdominal trauma. In spite of our best technology and advances in diagnostic equipment and supportive care, the morbidity and mortality remain high. The reason for this could be due to the interval between trauma and hospitalization, delay in diagnosis, inadequate and lack of appropriate surgical treatment, post-operative complications and associated trauma specially to head, thorax and extremities. [4][5]

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- To study the impact of blunt abdominal trauma on abdominal solid organs like spleen, liver and hollow viscera like stomach and intestine.
- To study various mode of injuries in blunt abdomen trauma.
- To study various modes of presentation in early diagnosis.
- To study various available investigations for detection of abdominal injuries.
- To study outcome of various management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Blunt abdominal trauma
2. Patient gives consent to participate in study

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Pregnant woman
2. Patient gives negative consent to participate in study

MATERIALS AND METHODS SOURCE OF DATA

SOURCE OF DATA:

This is a prospective study of blunt abdominal injuries during the period from June 2019 to January 2021 in Sheth Lallubhai Gordhandas Municipal General Hospital, Ahmedabad. Number of cases studied is 60.

METHODS OF COLLECTION OF DATA:

Clinical Data of admitted patient were collected by their detail history after stabilizing the patient, clinical examination with appropriate investigations. Routine blood Investigation like CBC and All sera tests were carried out in all the patients. This all collected data were documented in specially prepared Performa. On the basis of clinical findings and examination; further investigations were done such as plain erect x-ray abdomen, ultrasound and Contrast CT scan. The decision for operative or nonoperative management depended on the outcome of the clinical examination and results of diagnostic tests. Patients selected for nonoperative or conservative management were placed on strict immobilized with hourly pulse rate, blood

pressure, respiratory rate monitoring and repeated abdomen examination. Appropriate diagnostic tests especially ultrasound of abdomen was repeated as and when required. CECT scan was done in 21 patients in our study. Abdomen x -ray was done in all patients and Ultrasound of abdomen was done in 53 cases.

RESULTS

A) AGE INCIDENCE:

AGE GROUP (Years)	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
0-11	01	01.8
11-20	09	15.0
21-30	23	38.3
31-40	11	18.3
41-50	11	18.3
51-60	03	05.0
61-70	02	03.3
71-80	00	00

B) SEX INCIDENCE:

GENDER	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
Male	46	76
Female	14	24

C) RATIO OF OPERATIVE TO CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT:

	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
Operative	35	58
Conservative	25	42

D) MODE OF INJURY

CAUSATIVE AGENT	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
Road Traffic Accident	29	48
Fall From Height	11	18
Assault	20	34

E) SYMPTOMS AND SIGNS:

SYMPTOMS AND SIGNS	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
Abdo Pain	60	100
Vomiting	34	56.6
Nausea	42	70.0
Hematemesis	04	06.6
Haematuria	02	03.4
None	00	00

F) ASSOCIATED INJURIES:

ASSOCIATED INJURIES	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
Head Injuries	11	18.3
Chest Injury	04	06.6
Bone Fractures	06	10.0
Ligament or Muscle Injury	06	10.0

G) INVESTIGATIONS:

1) PLAIN X RAY ABDOMEN:

FEATURE	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
Soft tissue shadow	04	06.6

Free Gas Under Diaphragm	07	11.6
Multiple Air fluid Levels	03	05.0
Ground Glass Opacities	06	10.0
No Radiological Abnormality (NRA)	40	66.6

2) USG EXAMINATION:

ORGAN INJURED	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
Free fluid without solid organ Injury	01	01.7
Liver	12	20.0
Spleen	15	25.0
Kidney	08	13.3
Mesentery	04	06.7
Stomach	01	01.6
Intestine	11	18.3
Diaphragm	01	01.7
Multi Organ Injuries	07	11.6

3) OPERATIVE PROCEDURE:

Operative procedures	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
Splenectomy	11	18.3
splenorrhaphy	02	03.3
Hepatorraphy	10	16.6
Resection anastomosis	02	03.3
Mesenteric repair	03	05.0
Primary bowel repair	05	08.3
Gastric rupture repair	01	01.6
Nephrectomy	01	01.6

In the present study Males are predominantly affected and most of them fall in 21-30 years' age groups and most common mode of injury is Road Traffic Accident and in which most common injured organ is small intestine followed by spleen and liver. Majority of patients presented with complain of Abdomen Pain followed by Nausea and Vomiting. Plain erect abdomen Xray along with USG and CT helps in evaluation of abdomen organ injury. Proper Clinical examination and appropriate diagnostic test helps in management of blunt abdomen injury either Operative or Non-Operative management. Total 35 Patients selected for Operative management among them closure of bowel perforation was done in 5 patients, colostomy in 1 patient, repair of mesentery in 4 patients, splenorrhaphy in 2 patients and Splenectomy in 11 Patient, hepatorraphy in 10 patients and resection and anastomosis in 2 patients. 25 Patient selected for Non-Operative Management.

MORTALITY

In our present study 6 patients died in which 4 patients belonged to operative group and 2 patients died due to other associated injuries. No any patients died while being managed conservatively. Therefor the mortality in our study is 10%, this is comparable with other series published in our country. the mortality rate in Davis et al⁵ study is 13.3%, Di Vincenti et al¹⁰ study (1968) was 23%. Cox et al⁸ study reports a mortality rate of 10% [6]

DISCUSSION

In our study of 50 patients with blunt abdominal trauma males are majority affected and M: F ratio is 3:1, while in other studies like Madhumita Mukhopadhyay et al in their study of 47 patients who underwent laparotomy following intestinal injuries from blunt abdominal trauma over a period of 4 years found that the M: F ratio in this study was 8.4:112. Similarly, John L Kendall et al in a retrospective cohort study of 1169 cases of BAT reported that 66% of the affected individuals were Males [7]

Most common age group involved in our study is between 21 to 30 years as the age advances there is less chances of individuals getting assaulted and use of motor vehicle also decreases and the incidence of Blunt Abdo Trauma is found to be decreasing with the increasing age. Only 2 (3.3%) patients in our study were found to be above 60 years of age. Similar findings were reported by Davis et al who reported that 39% patients with Blunt Abdo Trauma belonged to age group of 21-40 years. [8]

The analysis of mode of injury revealed that Road traffic accidents were the most common mode of injury (48%) followed by fall from height (18%) and assault (20%). Similar Findings were reported by Khanna et al who found that t most common mode of injury in cases of BAT was Road Traffic accidents (57%). In contrast to our study Khanna et al in their study found assault (33%) to be more common than fall from height (15%). [9]

Associated injuries were present in 27 cases. The most extra abdominal injury was Head Injuries accounting for 18.3% followed by extremity fracture and pelvic fracture and ligament injuries in descending order. There was no association in 33 patients. Similar findings were reported by Nikhil Mehta et al in their retrospective study of 71 cases of Blunt Abdomen Trauma the authors found that the common associated injuries were head injuries (14%), haemothorax (14%) and rib fractures (20%). The authors managed most of the associated injuries conservatively except haemothorax and pneumothorax where intercostals drainage was needed. [10]

There is an increase in trend towards conservative management if the patient is haemodynamically stable. The injuries assessed by Contrast CT and Ultra Sonography and given grading was managed most of time conservatively. Minor lacerations and capsular tears which are difficult to diagnose clinically can be easily demonstrated in USG and CECT scan and were selected for non-operative management. The disadvantage of non-operative management is chances of miss some injuries which resulting in increased morbidity and mortality. Surgery is needed in vitally unstable patients and who are not responding to our conservative management with aggressive fluid resuscitation and with severe organ injuries. In our patients commonly we performed, primary repair of perforation, resection and anastomosis and splenectomy. Similar surgeries were required in patients of Blunt Abdo Trauma as reported by Wu CL et al AB. [11]

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This was a prospective study of 60 cases of blunt abdominal study, the following conclusions can be made.

- This Study is conducted in indoor Patients in the trauma ward of Sheth Lallubhai Gordhandas Municipal General Hospital, Ahmedabad in between 2019-2021. In Our Study Males are

predominantly affected and most of them fall in 21-30 years' age group which is young and reproductive age group.

- Most common forms of mode of injury are Road Traffic Accidents, Hence We required a Well-established Trauma Centres in every District hospital and good transportation services for transportation of patient from the accident site to the trauma Centre.
- Proper clinical examination and appropriate investigations helps in management of patient either operative or non-operative which leads successful treatment in these patients.
- In our study conservative management shows good output but still surgical management remains the main line of management.
- Xray Abdomen standing plain is a valuable investigation for gastrointestinal injuries.
- USG helps in identification of any solid organ injury or free fluid.
- The most common injured viscera in the present study are small bowel and they were managed by simple suturing followed by Splenic injury, majority of them were managed by splenectomy and Few of them were managed by splenorrhaphy. Liver injuries occupy the third position and were managed by hepatorrhaphy and Absorbable Gelatine Sponge packing.
- Associated extra abdominal injuries like head, thoracic and orthopaedic injuries were found in 29 cases in the present study.
- In Our Study Patients Presented with complain abdomen pain with nausea and vomiting.
- The present study showed a mortality of 10%.

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